

Prompt injection attacks and defenses in large language models: A systematic literature review

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Highlights

- First systematic literature review on prompt injection in LLMs.
- Identifies emerging prompt injection attack trends.
- Categorizes defenses into five main approaches, highlighting current limitations and open challenges.

Abstract

Prompt injection has rapidly emerged as a critical security threat in the deployment of large language models (LLMs), enabling adversaries to subvert intended behaviors and bypass safety mechanisms. Despite the increased attention that this threat has received, no previous studies have systematically analyzed the field. This paper presents the first systematic literature review (SLR) on prompt injection, with the objective of facilitating a comprehensive, evidence-based understanding of the existing attacks and defenses in LLM among researchers and practitioners. We extensively searched databases like ACM Digital Library, ScienceDirect and Web of Science, initially screening 207 studies and ultimately focusing on 56 relevant papers, based on rigorous inclusion, exclusion, and quality criteria. The analysis is structured around three core research questions: (i) the taxonomical classification of prompt injection attacks, (ii) the identification of recent and innovative attack techniques, and (iii) the characterization of proposed defense mechanisms. The findings reveal a rapidly evolving and multi-layered threat landscape, encompassing obfuscation strategies, automated and multi-modal attacks, and psychologically manipulative prompts. In response, the literature proposes a range of defenses, including input-level sanitization, model-level filtering, prompt engineering, classification-based approaches, and architectural safeguards.

Future research should focus on establishing robust standardization in both theory and experimentation, addressing the heterogeneity in attack classification and defense evaluation, while promoting empirical and quantitative approaches to assess effectiveness and considering user privacy and ethical implications.

Keywords: prompt injection, systematic literature review, llm

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1 Introduction

In recent years, large language models (LLMs) have emerged as a disruptive innovation. These advanced artificial intelligence systems possess the capacity to comprehend and generate text, images, and video, in addition to performing complex reasoning.

The adoption of these technologies is expanding, gradually crossing academic and industrial boundaries, and finding increasingly diverse applications in fields such as healthcare, law, finance, and cybersecurity. This ongoing and evolving process is profoundly transforming the technological and scientific landscape, highlighting not only opportunities but also new challenges, particularly concerning the security and reliability of these complex systems. The issue of security, vulnerabilities, and risks associated with LLMs application is of paramount importance today. According to the OWASP Top 10 for LLM Applications in 2025, the most significant threat identified is prompt injection.

Prompt injection is a vulnerability that *"occurs when user prompts alter the LLM's behavior or output in unintended ways. These inputs can affect the model even if they are imperceptible to humans, therefore prompt injections do not need to be human-visible/readable, as long as the content is parsed by the model."* (OWASP, 2025)

Due to the novelty of the topic, the scientific literature is constantly being updated, and in order to provide researchers and practitioners with a clear, evidence-based picture of this specific problem, a systematic review of the literature is needed.

In this review, we try to answer the following research questions (RQs):

RQ1: How can prompt injection attacks be systematically categorized and what taxonomy emerges from the current literature?

RQ2: What are the most recent and innovative prompt injection techniques for large generative language models identified in the scientific literature?

RQ3: What defense mechanisms have been proposed against prompt injection?

For this purpose, three different full text and bibliographic databases were used: ACM Digital Library, ScienceDirect and Web of Science.

In order to achieve our goal, the well-established guidelines by (Kitchenham et al., 2007) were followed.

By integrating the results of these studies, we aim to offer meaningful contributions for researchers and practitioners in the field, while also promoting further exploration in this area.

In order to facilitate a quick and structured review, some comparative tables are shown below that summarize various taxonomies (Table 1), attacks (Table 2) and defenses (Table 3) relevant to our results.

These tables provide a concise overview, allowing one to understand the essential techniques at a glance.

Table 1: Taxonomies

Reference	Type	Categories	Utility
(Xu et al., 2024a)	Prompt-level	Pretending, Privilege Escalation, Attention Shifting	Enables fine-grained prompt classification
(Ahmed and Jothi, 2024)	Attack-based	Attack strategies (e.g., automation, persuasion, multi-modal)	Supports threat modeling.
(Abdelnabi et al., 2023)	Threat-based	Threat types (e.g., fraud, intrusion, DoS)	
(Quintian et al., 2025)	Model-level	Mismatched Generalization, Competing Objectives, Adversarial Robustness, Mixed Attacks	Aids model robustness assessment.
(Bouamor et al., 2023)	Ontology	Instruction-based, Context Manipulation, Obfuscation and Encoding, Cognitive Attacks	Enables automated threat detection.

Table 2: Prompt Injection Attacks

Name	Type	Technique	Goal	Targeted Models	Max ASR	Reference
ArtPrompt	Obfuscation-based	ASCII-based obfuscation	Mask unsafe words with ASCII art representation	GPT-3.5, GPT-4, Gemini, Claude, Llama2	78%	(Jiang et al., 2024)
FuzzLLM	Automated prompt generation	Fuzzing and mutation	Generate diverse automated jailbreaking prompt	Vicuna, ChatGLM2, GPT-4 etc.	-	(Yao et al., 2024)
LLM-Fuzzer				gpt-3.5-turbo-0125 Llama-2-7B-Chat	89.20%	(Yu et al., 2024a)
PAP	Persuasion-based	Persuasion prompts	Humanize and Persuade LLMs as human-like communicators	Llama-2-7b-Chat, GPT-3.5, GPT-4	92%	(Zeng et al., 2024)
HADES	Multi-modal	Typographic obfuscation + Visual adversarial optimization	Multi-modal jailbreak via image obfuscation	LLaVA-1.5, Gemini Pro Vision,	90.26%	(Li et al., 2025)

Structure of the paper. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the LLM and its related work. Section 3 outlines the utilized methodology for SLR. Section 4 reports the analysis of the results. Section 5 discusses the results and their implications, and provides the future research lines. Section 6 reports the threats to the validity and the mitigation strategies applied. Section 7 concludes the paper.

2 Background and related work

LLMs are generative mathematical models of the statistical distribution of tokens, where the tokens in question include words, parts of words, or individual characters including punctuation marks (Shanahan, 2024). Complex architectures, such as Transformer based on attention mechanisms (Vaswani et al., 2017), underpin this.

Noteworthy examples include GPT-4 (OpenAI, 2023), BERT (Devlin et al., 2019) or Llama-4 (Meta, 2025). Certain models exhibit the capacity for reasoning, such as the o series (OpenAI, 2024) and DeepSeek-R1 (Guo et al., 2025).

Reinforcement learning algorithm teaches the model how to think productively using its chain of thought in a highly data-efficient training process (OpenAI, 2024).

Specific prompts are strategically employed to facilitate the model’s generation of accurate responses. In DeepSeek-R1, to first produce a reasoning process, followed by the final answer was used the template shown in Table 4 (Guo et al., 2025).

It is important to note that the word "**prompt**" will be replaced with the specific reasoning question during the training session.

Table 3: Prompt Injection Defenses

Category	Techniques	Application Level	Advantages	Limitations	References
Input-level Defenses	Delimiters, Preprocessing, Backtranslation	Pre-input	Lightweight, model-agnostic	Fragile against obfuscation and polymorphic attacks	(Liu et al., 2024a), (Pokhrel et al., 2024), (Wang et al., 2024)
Model-level Filtering and Alignment	Hidden State Filtering (HSF), SafeDecoding, Grad-Safe, Goal Prioritization, RAC - Robust Alignment Check	Inference-time	Direct access to model signals; proactive filtering	Requires access to model internals; possible latency overhead	(Qian et al., 2025), (Xu et al., 2024b), (Xie et al., 2024), (Zhang et al., 2024), (Cao et al., 2024a)
Prompt Engineering and Self-Constraint	Self-reminders, Chain-of-Thought prompting, Malice Evaluation	Prompt-level	Low implementation cost; no fine-tuning required	Susceptible to semantic manipulation or context shifts	(Xie et al., 2023), (Cao et al., 2024b), (Xu et al., 2024c)
Classification-based Approaches	Prompt-G, ToxicDetector, Legilimens, Linguistic Feature Detection, MoJE,	Post-output	High detection accuracy; modular and scalable	Depends on labeled data; false positives possible	(Pingua et al., 2024), (Liu et al., 2024b), (Wu et al., 2024), (Lee et al., 2023), (Cornacchia et al., 2024)
Architectural Systems	Pipeline, Vigil, ECSO, AdaShield	Jatmo, Prevention Tool	Integrated, multi-layered protection	Increased complexity and resource usage	(Gokcimen and Das, 2025), (Pokhrel et al., 2024), (Piet et al., 2024), (Gou et al., 2025), (Wang et al., 2025), (Chen et al., 2025)

Table 4: Template for DeepSeek-R1-Zero (Guo et al., 2025).

A conversation between User and Assistant. The user asks a question, and the Assistant solves it. The assistant first thinks about the reasoning process in the mind and then provides the user with the answer. The reasoning process and answer are enclosed within `<think>` `</think>` and `<answer>` `</answer>` tags, respectively, i.e., `<think>` reasoning process here `</think>` `<answer>` answer here `</answer>`. User: **prompt**. Assistant:

Direct prompt injection is achieved precisely by exploiting this LLM knowledge; in fact, it occurs when a user’s prompt input directly alters the behavior of the model in unexpected or unintended ways (OWASP, 2025).

It should be noted that the terms "prompt injection" and "jailbreaking" are frequently used interchangeably to denote a specific type of attack in which the user manipulates the LLM to execute an unintended action.

However, from a theoretical standpoint, these two terms do not completely align.

In (Ivanusca and Irimia, 2024) the conceptual difference between these two terms is clarified:

- **Jailbreaking** means to reverse engineer a system and exploit its vulnerabilities in order to have full control and privileges over the system. In this manner, we define a jailbreak attack as a vicious prompt which has an objective to bypass of any kind safety mechanism or ethical guidelines. This type of attack has as the end target the LLM itself.
- **Prompt injection** has its roots in the name of one the most “famous” vulnerabilities that plagued the Web, SQL injection. It is a vicious prompt that has as its objective to influence the output generated by the LLM, making it perform another task than the one it was supposed to or manipulating the model in generating vicious instruction that is passed further in the system. We observe that in this case, the end target is not necessarily the LLM. The LLM can act as a bridge that allows the attacker to damage other components that otherwise would not be accessible.

This theoretical difference is also highlighted on the *LLM security.net* portal. This collection contains links to research, papers, and news related to LLM security. It represents one of the first attempts made to try to shed light on attack and defense methodologies of LLMs and more generally to analyze the security of LLMs.

Nevertheless, while it constitutes a valid point of departure for navigating a rapidly evolving field of research such as prompt injection, it does not follow a structured scientific process as in the present work. The system in fact depends on two mechanisms: first, the submission of pull requests, and second, the publication of posts on X.com, which was previously known as twitter.com.

The present work is based on a systematic approach, including the application of an explicit protocol for source selection, transparent inclusion and exclusion criteria, and a critical assessment of source quality.

It is important to note that some work found in LLM Security was actually included in this review as well, e.g. (Abdelnabi et al., 2023) or (Xie et al., 2023), nevertheless, their presence is the result of a formal and replicable process of selection and analysis.

This process is aimed not only at cataloging existing contributions, but also at synthesizing the state of the art in a critical and structured way. The synthesis provides a solid basis for future research.

At this time, no scientific research has systematically characterized the phenomenon of prompt injection.

This review aims to address this critical gap by providing a meticulous mapping and critical synthesis of the scientific contributions.

3 Methodology

The following section outlines the protocol utilized for SLR. The method proposed by (Kitchenham et al., 2007) was applied in this study.

A systematic review is methodically structured in three phases: *Planning the review*, *Conducting the review*, *Reporting the review*.

This work focuses on prompt injection attacks and defenses in large language models and aims to take a snapshot of the current state of the art on this topic in order to identify the future direction of research in *computer science*.

3.1 Research question formulation

The review's main goal is to define the research questions and provide answers after assessing the information of the articles chosen.

The research questions that were addressed in this work can be found below:

RQ1: How can prompt injection attacks be systematically categorized and what taxonomy emerges from the current literature?

RQ2: What are the most recent and innovative prompt injection techniques for large generative language models identified in the scientific literature?

RQ3: What defense mechanisms have been proposed against prompt injection?

RQ1 enables a better understanding of the threat landscape, promotes comparative analysis, and supports the development of defensive frameworks.

RQ2 allows us to understand the most recent and innovative strategies for anticipating emerging threats and adapting defense systems accordingly.

RQ3 is essential for assess the effectiveness and limitations of LLM protection and security.

3.2 Search strategy

It is crucial to establish and follow a search strategy. We used a range of academic databases to compile the studies for our review, specifically: ACM Digital Library, ScienceDirect and Web of Science.

The search will be conducted on the *title*, *keywords* and *abstract*, as authors may address these subjects without necessarily incorporating specific terms in the title.

In contrast, conducting a full text search can yield a substantial number of false positives, as search terms may be present in unrelated contexts. In order to reduce noise and maximize relevance, the search will be limited to crucial sections of the documentation, such as the title and abstract.

This approach ensures a balance between breadth and precision. It allows the most relevant material to be collected without an excess of unrelated documents being collected.

Moreover, it should be noted that the queries were executed and are based on the results obtained on *29 May 2025*.

3.2.1 Search String

When formulating the search string in a systematic literature review, it is essential to strike a balance between breadth and precision.

The following search string is used in the different databases:

```
("jailbreak*" OR "prompt injection") AND ("large language model*" OR "LLM*")
```

This search string is made up of two parts:

1. **"jailbreak*" OR "prompt injection"**: These keywords are useful to obtain only domain-specific texts. In fact, while prompt injection and jailbreaking are related concepts in LLM security, they are often used interchangeably (OWASP, 2025).
2. **"large language model*" OR "LLM"**: They were used to obtain specific literature. The literature focused on LLMs and avoiding ambiguities.

As illustrated in Table 5, the search strings are adapted to specific databases. It is important to note that papers from 2020, year of GPT-3 release, until 2025 were considered.

Table 5: Search strings and resulting entries

Database	Search string	Results
ACM - Title	"query": {Title:(("jailbreak*" OR "prompt injection") AND ("large language model*" OR "LLM*"))} "filter": {E-Publication Date: Past 5 years, ACM Content: DL}	3
ACM - Keyword	"query": {Keyword:(("jailbreak*" OR "prompt injection") AND ("large language model*" OR "LLM*"))} "filter": {E-Publication Date: Past 5 years, ACM Content: DL}	5
ACM - Abstract	"query": {Abstract:(("jailbreak*" OR "prompt injection") AND ("large language model*" OR "LLM*"))} "filter": {E-Publication Date: Past 5 years, ACM Content: DL}	14
Web of Science	AB=((("jailbreak*" OR "prompt injection") AND ("large language model*" OR "LLM*"))	83
ScienceDirect	((("jailbreak?" OR "prompt injection") AND ("large language model?" OR "LLM?"))	102

3.3 Eligibility criteria definition

In this review, the eligibility criteria were divided into the following:

- **Inclusion Criteria:** The article will be included if all criteria are met. (Table 6)
- **Exclusion Criteria:** The article will be discarded if any of these criteria are satisfied. (Table 7)
These criteria were applied through database filters.
- **Quality Criteria:** The article will be evaluated based on quality criteria, and those that do not meet a specific threshold will be discarded. (Table 8)
Each criterion was rated using a three-point scale: Yes (2 points), Partially (1 point), No (0 points). The inclusion threshold is four points.

3.4 Study selection process

The initial phase of the research involved a search of the identified databases, resulting in the retrieval of 207 articles.

Following an initial evaluation of the titles and abstracts, 109 articles were rejected, primarily due to their lack of relevance to LLM. In addition, 19 duplicates were removed. After a full-text review, we got 56 studies.

Our study selection process is shown in Figure 1.

Table 6: Inclusion Criteria

Code	Name	Description
IC1	Focus on LLM	The paper should specifically focus on identifying LLM’s attacks or defenses.
IC2	Practical Application	The paper provides cases or examples of the practical application of LLM’s attacks or defenses.
IC3	Implementation Details	The paper must provide explicit strategies, methods or steps on the implementation of LLM’s attack or defences.

Table 7: Exclusion Criteria

Code	Name	Description
EC1	English Language	Articles not published in English must be excluded.
EC2	Duplicated articles	The same articles that appear in multiple digital libraries should be counted only once.
EC3	Articles written before 2020	Before 2020, LLMs were not widely used, so the article written before this time must be excluded.

In addition, an analysis of the type of articles reveals that a substantial percentage of studies, amounting to approximately 70%, are disseminated through conference presentations. This serves as a certification of the contemporary relevance of our review. The selection of the final studies was documented by creating a Google Sheet file, which is available upon request and includes the reasons for exclusion after a full-text review.

4 Results

This section presents the main findings of the systematic literature review, which is structured according to the research questions (RQs) defined above. A detailed analysis of the selected studies was performed to extract relevant insights that directly address each research question.

4.1 RQ1: How can prompt injection attacks be systematically categorized and what taxonomy emerges from the current literature?

The current literature reveals a complex and multidimensional landscape of taxonomies developed to categorize prompt injection attacks targeting large language models (LLMs).

Table 8: Quality Criteria

Code	Name	Description
QC1	Relevance	Is the study directly relevant to prompt injection and LLMs?
QC2	Rigor	Does the study provide a clear methodology and sufficient detail to ensure reproducibility or verification?
QC3	Evidence	Are claims supported by empirical data, case studies, experiments, or solid theoretical analysis?

Figure 1: Study selection process

These taxonomies differ in scope, granularity, and underlying theoretical assumptions, ranging from prompt-level tactics to model vulnerabilities and application-level threats.

This section summarizes and compares these taxonomies.

4.1.1 Prompt level taxonomy

(Xu et al., 2024a) propose a two-level taxonomy derived from empirical analysis of 78 jailbreak prompts. At the first level, the prompts are grouped into three high-level

strategies:

- **Pretending:** Modifying context while preserving the malicious intent (e.g., role-playing).
- **Privilege Escalation:** Requesting elevated authority (e.g., “sudo” mode).
- **Attention Shifting:** Redirecting the model’s task to bypass safeguards (e.g., story continuation).

The second level identifies ten prompt patterns aligned with these strategies. These patterns reflect recurring linguistic and rhetorical structures used to induce model misbehavior.

The classification is as follows:

- **Pretending strategy**
 - **Character Role Play (CR):** Assigns the model a fictional persona to bypass safety constraints by simulating alternate identities.
 - **Assumed Responsibility (AR):** Frames the prompt as authorized or legitimate by invoking responsibility or approval disclaimers.
 - **Research Experiment (RE):** Presents the prompt as part of a controlled scientific or academic test to encourage compliance.
- **Privilege Escalation strategy**
 - **Superior Model (SUPER):** Claims the model is an advanced or unrestricted version with elevated capabilities to override limits.
 - **Sudo Mode (SUDO):** Uses command line privilege escalation metaphors to request higher access permissions.
 - **Simulate Jailbreaking (SIMU):** Frames the jailbreak request as a simulation to reduce perceived rule violation.
- **Attention Shifting strategy**
 - **Text Continuation (TC):** Embed harmful content within a longer narrative or code snippet to exploit autocomplete behavior.
 - **Logical Reasoning (LOGIC):** Guides the model through stepwise reasoning to circumvent restrictions and reveal forbidden information.
 - **Program Execution (PROG):** Simulates code or scripting environments to elicit restricted outputs under the guise of functional completion.
 - **Translation (TRANS):** Uses foreign languages or encoded text to hide unsafe content and requests it indirectly via translation.

These patterns reveal that prompt injection exploits not only model weaknesses but also human-like conversational assumptions (e.g., trust, simulation, authority).

Importantly, 71% of jailbreak prompts combine multiple patterns, underscoring the need for multi-layered detection and mitigation strategies.

4.1.2 Attack-Based Taxonomy

(Ahmed and Jothi, 2024) classify jailbreak attacks according to the attack methodology. They identify three categories:

- **Automated Red Teaming:** Includes payload obfuscation, iterative prompt refinement, and code injection.
- **Persuasion and Deception:** Exploits emotional framing and nested instructions.
- **Multimodal Jailbreaking:** Use input across modalities (e.g., image-text) to bypass filters.

This taxonomy reflects the shift from manual attacks to automated and scalable adversarial pipelines.

It is well suited for analyzing the evolution and generalization of attack strategies.

4.1.3 Model-level Taxonomy

The taxonomy of (Quintian et al., 2025) focuses on the failure modes of LLMs.

It includes:

- **Mismatched Generalization:** The model answers unsafe prompts due to gaps in safety coverage.
- **Competing Objectives:** The model prioritizes helpfulness over harmlessness.
- **Adversarial Robustness:** The model fails under input perturbations (e.g., synonyms, noise).
- **Mixed Attacks:** Combinatory methods targeting multiple vulnerabilities simultaneously.

This framework is valuable for understanding the underlying causes of vulnerability beyond surface-level prompt features, therefore, this contributes to the evaluation of the robustness of the model.

4.1.4 Threat-Based Taxonomy

(Abdelnabi et al., 2023) offer a taxonomy focused on the security impact of indirect prompt injection in deployed systems. Threat categories include:

- **Information Gathering:** Leakage of user data or context.
- **Fraud:** Generation of phishing or scam content.
- **Intrusion:** Unauthorized control of systems.
- **Malware:** Self-replicating or malicious prompt behavior.
- **Manipulated Content:** Biased or false outputs.
- **Denial of Service:** Prompt chains that degrade model performance.

This taxonomy abstracts from specific techniques and instead captures the real-world implications of prompt injection across application domains; moreover, it supports threat modeling.

4.1.5 Ontological Taxonomy of Prompt Hacking Techniques

(Bouamor et al., 2023) provide a high-resolution, data-driven ontology built from over 600,000 adversarial prompts.

Key categories in the ontology include:

- **Instruction-based attacks** (e.g., Simple and Compound Instructions).
- **Context manipulation** techniques (e.g., Context Overflow, Context Switching, Separators).
- **Obfuscation** and encoding strategies (e.g., Syntactic Transformations, Typos, Translation).
- **Task deflection and cognitive attacks**, which include Few-Shot Prompting, Role-Play-based Virtualization, and Payload Splitting.

This ontological approach marks a methodological advancement: it captures the combinatorial and evolving nature of prompt hacking and enables fine-grained analysis across different abstraction levels, from prompt syntax to model-level failure to system behavior.

Its scalability and granularity make it particularly suited for deployment in automated threat detection pipelines and in the creation of annotated datasets for red-teaming, benchmarking, and adversarial training.

4.1.6 Summary

The current literature presents multiple taxonomies of prompt injection and jailbreak attacks, each offering a distinct perspective on the phenomenon. Some focus on the structure and strategies of adversarial prompts, others classify attacks based on attacker intent, model vulnerabilities, or real-world threats.

When considered together, these taxonomies provide a richer and more layered understanding of prompt hacking, capturing its technical, behavioral, and systemic dimensions. This multiplicity highlights the complexity of the attack surface and suggests that a comprehensive defense requires integrating the insights from all these complementary points of view.

4.2 RQ2: What are the most recent and innovative prompt injection techniques for large generative language models identified in the scientific literature?

The methods used to attack LLMs are subject to continuous evolution. The analytical process yielded the identification of four distinct categories of recent and innovative prompt injection strategies: (1) Obfuscation-Based Attacks, (2) Automated Prompt Generation, (3) Persuasion-based Techniques, and (4) Multimodal and Visual Attacks.

4.2.1 Obfuscation-based Attacks

Obfuscation attacks attempt to bypass safety filters by encoding or transforming the prompt in a way that hides its malicious intent while preserving its semantic meaning for the LLM.

- **Textual Encoding:** Techniques such as Base64, leetspeak, ROT13, and disemvowelment² allow adversaries to encode dangerous queries that remain intelligible to the model but are likely to evade superficial lexical filters.
- **Mathematical Function-Based Encoding:** Introduced in (Kwon and Pak, 2024), this method encodes sensitive terms through 2D geometric functions, directing the LLM to interpret visual plots as linguistic characters.
- **ASCII Art-Based Injection:** ArtPrompt (Jiang et al., 2024) masks unsafe content as ASCII art, leveraging the LLM’s contextual capabilities to infer the obscured message.
- **Disguised Harmful Instruction (DRA):** By reconstructing malicious instructions from embedded characters (Liu et al., 2024c), DRA-style attacks challenge models trained to avoid direct content.
- **Syntax Tree-Based Obfuscation:** IntentObfuscator³ constructs adversarial prompts by applying syntactic tree transformations, thus creating multiple ambiguous or semantically overloaded interpretations that hinder content moderation.
- **Universal Perturbation Model:** (Mangaokar et al., 2024) to bypass LLMs safety mechanism uses universal adversary perturbations: textual patterns designed to constantly trigger malicious output. These perturbations are embedded in prompts and are difficult for both humans and automated filters to detect. The attack remains effective even when evaluated by safety classifiers like LlamaGuard, which often misclassify malicious outputs as safe. The method demonstrates high transferability across models and highlights a critical vulnerability in current alignment strategies. It underscores the need for more robust and context-aware defense mechanisms in LLMs.

²(Wei et al., 2023), (Bouamor et al., 2023)

³(Shang et al., 2024)

4.2.2 Automated Prompt Generation

This class of attacks employs optimization algorithms, mutation strategies, or LLM-in-the-loop pipelines to automatically generate and refine jailbreak prompts, enabling efficient and scalable adversarial prompting.

- **Genetic algorithms (GAs):** are an automated, black-box method that mimics natural evolution to optimize universal adversarial prompts, enabling them to iteratively bypass large language model (LLM) safety mechanisms and elicit harmful or unintended responses without requiring access to the model’s internal parameters. (Lapid et al., 2024)
- **Fuzzing-Based Frameworks:** FuzzLLM (Yao et al., 2024) and LLM-Fuzzer (Yu et al., 2024a) use mutation techniques (e.g., rephrase, crossover) on base templates to create new adversarial examples.
- **Simple black-box attack:** (Takemoto, 2024) uses the target model itself to rewrite a harmful query in less detectable forms, often achieving high attack success rates within a few iterations.
- **Compositional Instruction Attack (CIA) framework:** (Jiang et al., 2025a) breaks down malicious tasks into seemingly benign subtasks, such as fictional writing or dataset creation, thereby reducing detection probability.

4.2.3 Persuasion-based

This category encompasses jailbreak techniques that exploit psychological and rhetorical strategies to bypass LLM safety mechanisms.

- **PAP - Persuasive adversarial prompts:** (Zeng et al., 2024) introduces a persuasion taxonomy and demonstrates that persuasive adversarial prompts can reliably jailbreak LLMs across multiple risk categories, outperforming standard attack methods and evading most existing defenses.
- **SpearBot:** (Qi et al., 2025) presents a two-stage framework that uses GPT-4 to generate and iteratively optimize spear-phishing emails, achieving high deception and evasion rates against both machine and human evaluators.

4.2.4 Multi-modal and Visual Prompt Injection

- **HADES:** New jailbreak method that links image-based typographic obfuscation and adversarial visual optimization to jailbreak multi-modal LLMs, introduced by (Li et al., 2025).

It is a new three-phase jailbreak method that conceals malicious intent from text to image through typography, amplifies the harmfulness of the image with LLM (generating optimized images with diffusion models), and further strengthens it with adversarial images generated through gradient updating.

- **Visual Adversarial images:** A single adversarial image can force an aligned model to follow otherwise blocked instructions (Qi et al., 2024). In addition, text within images or a combination of images and text can facilitate prompt injection attacks. (Sharma et al., 2024)
- **Speech attack:** The voice mode integrated within LLMs demonstrates vulnerability to adversarial disruption, with an attack success rate of 90%. (Peri et al., 2024)

4.2.5 Other Attack Techniques

In addition to the categories previously discussed, several other studies provide valuable insights that contribute to the ongoing discovery and formalization of novel prompt injection and jailbreak strategies.

A concise summary of these studies is presented in Table 9.

4.2.6 Summary

This section discusses advanced prompt injection techniques designed to create prompt injection in large-language models. These methods exploit encoding schemes, automated generation strategies, and psychological manipulation to bypass filters and elicit harmful outputs.

Recent developments also extend to multi-modal inputs like images and speech, revealing critical vulnerabilities in current alignment and defense systems.

These techniques are evolving rapidly and becoming increasingly sophisticated and transferable across models.

Emerging concerns also include hardware level vulnerabilities, , particularly in the domain of LLM-aided design - LAD (Wan et al., 2024).

This underscores the urgent need for robust and adaptive mitigation strategies.

4.3 RQ3: What defense mechanisms have been proposed against prompt injection?

Prompt injection techniques are rapidly evolving, with attackers continuously adapting strategies to circumvent existing safeguards.

Recent findings, such as those from the JailbreakHub framework (Shen et al., 2024), demonstrate that even state-of-the-art models remain vulnerable to increasingly subtle and transferable jailbreak prompts.

Despite the deployment of internal and external safeguards, modern defenses often fail to provide reliable protection.

This underscores the urgent need to identify and analyze effective defense approaches.

The reviewed literature presents a diverse range of defense mechanisms against prompt injection attacks in Large Language Models (LLMs) that can be categorized into five

overarching groups: (1) Input-level defenses, (2) Model-level filtering and alignment methods, (3) prompt engineering and self-constraint methods, (4) Classification-based, and (5) Architectural systems.

4.3.1 Input-level defenses

These techniques aim to sanitize or structure the input in a way that prevents the injection of malicious instruction.

- **Delimiters and Sandwich Prevention:** Defensive prompt structuring that isolates user-provided data from the system prompt via XML tags or similar, e.g. triple backtick, combined with reminders of the task before and after user input (Liu et al., 2024a).
- **Prompt Preprocessing:** Normalization steps that include tokenization, lemmatization, and character casing to reduce the surface of prompt manipulation. This is just one part of the process. Later, we will discuss Vigil (Pokhrel et al., 2024) in more detail.
- **Backtranslation:** We can uncover the original intent, by deducing a "backtranslated prompt" from the model's initial response. It is often hidden and may be harmful. Because this inferred prompt is based on the model output rather than the attacker's altered input, the system can reject the original request if the backtranslated prompt is recognized as harmful. (Wang et al., 2024).

4.3.2 Model level filtering and alignment method

This category includes techniques that modify or evaluate model internals or generation process.

- **Hidden State Filtering (HSF):** (Qian et al., 2025) uses hidden vectors from LLM decoder layers to classify prompts as harmful or benign at inference time. The process consists of two phases: Phase 1 involves training a weak classifier, a simple MLP, to learn a "harmfulness score" from hidden vectors of harmful and benign queries, while Phase 2 integrates this classifier into the LLM to preemptively interrupt inference and refuse responses if the score exceeds a specified threshold.
- **SafeDecoding:** (Xu et al., 2024b) intervenes during token generation, modifying decoding strategies (e.g., top-k, nucleus) to suppress harmful completions. The process consists of fine-tuning the original LLM to create a safer expert model during training, and in inference, it uses both models to generate a new token probability distribution that diminishes tokens aligned with attacker goals and enhances those aligned with human values, applying this adjustment only to the first two tokens while generating the rest through standard decoding.
- **GradSafe:** A gradient-based filtering method that computes cosine similarity gaps between safe and unsafe prompt pairs (Xie et al., 2024).
- **Goal Prioritization:** A plug-and-play prompting strategy that forces the model to prefer safety over helpfulness during ambiguous tasks (Zhang et al., 2024).

- **Robust Alignment Check (RAC):** (Cao et al., 2024a) introduces stochastic token dropping to test the robustness of alignment and infer model behavior on corrupted prompts.

4.3.3 Prompt engineering and self-constraint methods

This set of methods includes defense mechanisms that utilize or manipulate prompts to influence model behavior proactively.

- **Self-Reminder:** Embeds ethical constraints within system prompts to continuously remind the model of safety priorities (Xie et al., 2023). This defense technique is also mentioned by (Xu et al., 2024d).
- **Chain-of-Thought Prompting:** (Cao et al., 2024b) encourages stepwise reasoning to resist misleading instructions. It is a multi-stage defense that evolves in five different stages:
 1. **Initial Guidance Setup:** Encourages responsible, step-by-step reasoning to prevent harmful content.
 2. **Intention Analysis:** Analyzes user query intentions and evaluates permissibility based on ethics and legality.
 3. **Attempt to Respond:** Generates an initial response while ensuring responsible communication.
 4. **Self-reflection:** Assesses the response for potential illegal or harmful content.
 5. **Self-refinement:** Refines the response by refusing harmful queries and explaining the refusal.
- **Malice Evaluation:** (Xu et al., 2024c) introduces prompt tuning techniques (zero-shot and few-shot) that allow LLMs to self-assess the malice of their output and guide themselves away from harmful content generation.

4.3.4 Classification-based

These are model-agnostic systems that evaluate generated content or prompts after the initial LLM output.

- **Prompt-G:** (Pinguia et al., 2024) uses vector-based semantic similarity to identify harmful prompts and prevent unsafe responses.
- **ToxicDetector:** (Liu et al., 2024b) uses LLM-generated “concept descriptions”. These concept prompts are used as a higher-order abstraction in feature extraction and fed into classifiers trained to generalize across varied prompt formulations.
- **Legilimens:** (Wu et al., 2024) introduces an efficient and unified content moderation approach using probing of concept based on decoder architecture. It extracts features only from the first and last output tokens, termed I-moderation (input-focused) and O-moderation (output-focused).

- **Linguistic Feature Detection:** (Lee et al., 2023) presents a detailed analysis of jailbreak prompt features (e.g., aliasing, indirect phrasing, syntactic obfuscation), showing promise for improving classifier robustness based on syntax, lexicon, and semantics.
- **MoJE:** (Cornacchia et al., 2024) adopts an ensemble-based approach, combining the predictions of multiple classifiers trained on diverse jailbreak and benign datasets. By aggregating uncertainty estimates across classifiers, MoJE reduces false positives, a critical metric in high-sensitivity moderation pipelines, and achieves AUC (0.9947) and accuracy (0.9944) on benchmark datasets.

4.3.5 Architectural systems

These frameworks integrate multiple layers of defense and are designed for practical deployment in LLM-integrated applications.

- **Comprehensive Security Architecture:** (Gokcimen and Das, 2025) exemplifies a comprehensive, automated pipeline that integrates transformer-based classifiers for input sanitization, cross-LLM verification strategies to cross-check outputs from multiple models (e.g., GPT-4, Gemini), and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) modules to ground user queries semantically. This system culminates in an eligibility scoring mechanism that filters generated outputs based on toxicity, regulatory compliance, and topical sensitivity.
- **Vigil:** (Pokhrel et al., 2024) employs a scan ensemble architecture, comprising vector database searches, signature-based YARA rules and machine learning classifiers, to assign threat scores to prompts, enabling proactive filtering and integration into LLM-driven applications via REST APIs.
- **Jatmo:** A task-specific fine-tuning strategy trained on synthetic injection scenarios that makes models robust by design (Piet et al., 2024). Single-task models sacrifice versatility, but this may be acceptable for LLM-integrated applications.
- **ECISO:** (Gou et al., 2025) transform image input into descriptive text to make them compatible with existing textual moderation frameworks, a crucial capability given the difficulty of detecting embedded visual threats in multimodal systems.
- **Adaptive Prompt Refinement (AdaShield):** (Wang et al., 2025) create an adaptive auto-refinement framework that generates a diverse pool of optimized defense prompts using a target MLLM and a Defender LLM, which are then adaptively prepended to input queries to safeguard Multimodal Large Language Models (MLLMs) from structure-based jailbreak attacks without requiring fine-tuning or significantly compromising their general capabilities.
- **Prevention Tool:** (Chen et al., 2025) introduces a modular defense tool composed of two main components: a Jailbreak Attack Detector, responsible for identifying malicious or adversarial inputs, and an Ethics Evaluator, which assesses the ethicality or harmfulness of the content. The system uses DistilBERT as the backbone for harmfulness detection, leveraging its efficiency and accuracy for real-time evaluation.

4.3.6 Summary

Recent studies propose a diverse set of defense strategies against prompt injection, ranging from input sanitization and inference-time interventions to model prompting techniques.

Many approaches focus on suppressing harmful completions, guiding the model’s behavior through ethical constraints, or enhancing robustness through auxiliary classifiers.

Others introduce full-stack systems that combine detection, alignment, and filtering in practical applications. In general, the literature reflects a shift towards integrated and context-sensitive defenses that balance security, usability, and performance.

Additionally, (Mai et al., 2025) highlights a persistent dilemma: strengthening security often comes at the cost of model usability and responsiveness.

More capable LLMs may paradoxically exhibit greater vulnerability, underscoring the need to find a careful equilibrium between defensive rigor and functional utility.

5 Discussion, implications, and future work

The systematic literature review underscored various observations that require further investigation and that can serve as a foundation for potential future research studies.

5.1 Addressing research questions

In response to RQ1, the analysis reveals a fragmented but rich taxonomy landscape. Five distinct classifications have been identified: (i) prompt-level (e.g., role-playing, escalation, attention shifting), (ii) attacker-based (e.g., automated, persuasive, multimodal), (iii) model-level (e.g., competing objectives, robustness issues), (iv) threat-based taxonomies (e.g., fraud, DoS), and (v) large-scale ontologies based on adversarial prompt corpora. Each of these approaches offers a distinct perspective on the issue, yet the establishment of a recognized standard taxonomy could facilitate shared formalization of the phenomenon, allowing for the development of common theoretical models. Furthermore, such a taxonomy would promote semantic consistency across diverse studies, thus preventing ambiguity. It is important to note that the different taxonomies show different views important to highlighting different aspects on security.

In addressing RQ2, the review identifies four predominant trends in innovative prompt injection techniques: (i) obfuscation-based attacks that evade LLM security filters (e.g., textual encoding, ASCII Art injection, mathematical Function encoding), (ii) automated prompt generation pipelines employing genetic algorithms or fuzzing (e.g., genetic algorithms, fuzzing), (iii) persuasive prompt engineering leveraging psychological manipulation, and (iv) multi-modal attacks that exploit inputs such as images and speech. These techniques are increasingly transferable across models and highlight the ongoing arms race between attackers and defenders.

In order to respond to RQ3, the literature proposes a wide array of defensive strategies. These strategies can be grouped into five overarching categories, each addressing

different stages of the model input-output pipeline: i) input-level sanitization (e.g., delimiters, preprocessing, backtranslation), (ii) model-level filtering and alignment (e.g., HSF - hidden state filtering, SafeDecoding, goal prioritization), (iii) prompt engineering and self-constraint (e.g., self-reminder, chain-of-thought prompting), (iv) classification-based detection, and (v) architectural systems. Many approaches focus on suppressing harmful completions, others introduce full-stack system. Nevertheless, to date, no single defense provides holistic protection. Effective mitigation likely requires a layered and adaptive approach, integrating multiple mechanisms across different abstraction levels.

5.1.1 Summary

- RQ1: Five distinct taxonomies, each providing unique security perspectives, underscoring the need for a standardized taxonomy to enhance semantic consistency and develop common theoretical models.
- RQ2: Four key trends in innovative prompt injection techniques demonstrating their transferability across models and the ongoing arms race between attackers and defenders.
- RQ3: Five categories of defensive strategies against prompt injection, highlighting that no single defense offers complete protection and that effective mitigation requires a layered, adaptive approach.

5.2 Literature gaps

The results of this review underscore several significant knowledge gaps in the literature, which reflect the rapidly evolving nature of prompt injection research in Large Language Models (LLMs). First and foremost, the domain of prompt injection represents a relatively recent area of research characterized by continuous and rapid development. The rapid emergence of novel attack techniques and defensive strategies has led to significant challenges in establishing a stable and comprehensive state of the art. This dynamic environment encourages innovation; but it also leads to the fragmentation of knowledge and creates significant challenges for consolidation and reproducibility. A significant limitation is the absence of systematic comparative studies, including qualitative analyses. Currently, there is an absence of a shared analytical framework or reference model that enables researchers to meaningfully compare different categories of attacks or the effectiveness of proposed defenses. This discrepancy is further accentuated by the lack of standardized evaluation methodologies and the testing of many proposed approaches under heterogeneous conditions. It is important to note that many of the studies included in the current literature are based on outdated or open-source language models, such as GPT-3.5, Vicuna, or early variants of LLaMA. In the context of rapidly evolving model capabilities and alignment mechanisms, results derived from earlier architectures may no longer accurately represent the behavior of more recent systems. This prompts inquiries into the temporal validity and relevance of various experimental results, underscoring the necessity for continuous updating of the empirical foundation of prompt injection research.

5.3 Future directions

A primary area of future research concerns the necessity to promote robust and collectively established forms of standardization, both in theory and through experimental investigation. The current literature, while comprehensive and varied, is marked by significant heterogeneity in the classification of attacks and the evaluation of defenses. This fragmentation complicates the process of comparing studies. For instance, the implementation of a scientifically validated standard taxonomy could serve as a preliminary step. Concurrently, there is a marked necessity to direct research toward empirical and quantitative approaches that can overcome the inherent limitations of purely qualitative analyses. To this end, a quantitative classification of metrics is imperative to assess the effectiveness of attacks and defenses. Furthermore, additional systematic studies with a focus on the aspects of the impact of attacks and defenses on user privacy, as well as ethical considerations, would be valuable.

6 Threats to validity

This section discusses the potential threats to the validity of the study and the measures implemented to mitigate them.

The identification and organization of the threats was conducted in accordance with the well-known framework proposed by (Wohlin et al., 2012).

The main threat to construct validity is the formulation of the search string. To mitigate this threat, different keywords and their synonyms related to prompt injection and LLMs was utilized. Wildcard characters are also employed to capture variations of the keywords.

Threat to internal validity concerns the methodological rigor with which the review was conducted, particularly regarding study selection and data extraction. However, clear criteria for inclusion, exclusion and quality have been established to address this threat.

Concerning external validity, the literature’s coverage may constitute a potential issue. The literature identified and reviewed in this study may only represent a portion of the work related to prompt injection. To address this threat, multiple research databases were utilized.

The synthesis and interpretation of study results may compromise conclusion validity. To address this challenge, a systematic and transparent approach was employed to summarize and interpret the study results.

7 Conclusion

This systematic literature review has examined the current state of prompt injection attacks and defenses in large language models (LLMs). As indicated by the scientific literature, prompt injection represents an emerging challenge, with the potential to ensure the safety, reliability, and trustworthiness of LLM-driven systems.

Utilizing a rigorous methodology based on established guidelines proposed by (Kitchenham et al., 2007), a review of 56 high-quality studies was conducted, selected from major digital libraries. This review addressed three fundamental research questions (RQs), providing a critical mapping of the current state of the field.

Prompt injection attacks are currently categorized through diverse and non-standardized taxonomies, reflecting the lack of a unified conceptual framework. Emerging attack techniques include obfuscation, automated prompt generation, persuasive manipulation, and multimodal inputs, which increasingly evade existing defenses. Proposed countermeasures span input filtering, model-level alignment, prompt engineering, and post-hoc detection, but remain fragmented and lack robust, standardized evaluation.

Despite its structured, evidence-based approach to summarizing the rapidly evolving landscape of prompt injection, this review is subject to several limitations that must be acknowledged. Firstly, a statistical was not performed, consequently, the analysis is primarily qualitative and interpretive rather than empirical or predictive. Secondly, it should be noted that this review does not include experimental validation or reproduction of the defenses or attacks described. Thirdly, this work is restricted to currently published literature. Given the rapid evolution of the field, it is possible that the exclusion of recently published external work may have occurred.

There are notable gaps in the literature, such as the lack of systematic quantitative studies and standardized evaluation methodologies, reliance on outdated models, and concerns about the temporal validity of experimental results in the rapidly evolving field of rapid injection research.

Future research should focus on establishing robust standardization in both theory and experimentation, addressing the heterogeneity in attack classification and defense evaluation, while promoting empirical and quantitative approaches to assess effectiveness and considering user privacy and ethical implications.

It is hoped that this analysis will inspire new innovative efforts for greater effectiveness in implementing defenses and attacks against the greatest current threat to LLM security.

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Table 9: Additional studies on prompt injection techniques

Paper	Main Contribution
(Hu et al., 2025)	Proposes SC-Attack and SC-COLD, two scene-based jailbreak techniques that embed harmful prompts into narrative templates to increase plausibility and evade safety filters.
(Vajrobol et al., 2024)	Presents a multilingual study on instruction attacks in Thai, using a Bi-GRU + XLM-RoBERTa model to detect six categories of manipulative prompts with high accuracy.
(Ivanusca and Irimia, 2024)	Explores the security implications of prompting techniques, distinguishing between prompt injection and jailbreak attacks, and introduces the HOUYI framework for injection modeling.
(Liu et al., 2024a)	Analyzes prompt injection in LLM-integrated applications, emphasizing how malicious data embedded in user contexts (e.g., resumes, web pages) can subvert intended outputs.
(Yu et al., 2024b)	Conducts a systematic categorization of real-world jailbreak prompts, identifying recurring patterns such as roleplay, persona alteration, and hybrid strategies, and evaluating their effectiveness.
(Chang et al., 2024)	Proposes the "Puzzler" method to generate targeted offensive prompts using alignment-aware filtering, enabling red-teaming of LLMs based on malicious content objectives.
(Yi et al., 2024)	Investigates the "Reverse Alignment" phenomenon, revealing how positional bias and decoding heuristics can be exploited to increase the likelihood of harmful completions in open-access LLMs.
(Zhan et al., 2024)	Introduces INJECAGENT, a benchmark for indirect prompt injection attacks against tool-integrated LLM agents, highlighting critical vulnerabilities in system-LLM interactions.
(Shi et al., 2024)	Presents JudgeDeceiver, a universal attack framework targeting LLM-as-a-judge models, capable of biasing model evaluation via strategically injected sequences.
(Shen et al., 2024)	.
(Jiang et al., 2025b)	Develops MIF, a modular framework that dissects jailbreak prompts into reusable components (e.g., ciphering, narrative framing), enabling cross-domain transferability of attack patterns.